

Salicylaldehyde 4-Methoxybenzoylhydrazone and Diacetylbis(4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone) as Ligands for Tin, Lead and Zirconium

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The synthesis and characterisation of tin(II), tin(IV), organotin(IV), lead(II), organolead(IV), zirconium(IV) and organozirconium(IV) complexes with two new ligands salicylaldehyde 4-methoxybenzoyl hydrazone and diacetylbis(4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone) [abbreviated to (H_2) SMBHON and (H_2) DAMBHON, respectively] are described. Some reactions of isolated $Sn(DAMBHON)Cl_2$, with $MeSH$, $SiMe_3(NMe_3)$, $C_6H_5CH_2SiMe_3$, and $p-Me_3SiC_6H_4SiMe_3$, are discussed. The complexes isolated have been characterised by elemental analyses, molar conductance values, molecular weights and spectroscopic (uv-visible, ir and 1H nmr) data.

IN recent years there is growing interest on the chemistry of hydrazides and hydrazones owing to their biological activity¹⁻³ and analytical applications⁴. Besides, hydrazides and hydrazones have interesting ligational properties due to the presence of several potential coordination sites^{5,6}, and transition metal complexes of these ligands have been synthesised⁶⁻¹⁰ earlier. The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of some tin, lead and zirconium complexes of salicylaldehyde 4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone ((H_2) -SMBHON) and diacetylbis(4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone) ((H_2) DAMBHON).

Although metal complexes of many aroylhydrazones have been studied in recent years, no reports are available on the metal complexes of (H_2) SMBHON and (H_2) DAMBHON. However, very recently 2,6-diacetylpyridinebis(4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone) has been used to synthesise tin(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes^{11,12}.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands :

(H_2) SMBHON : Salicylaldehyde (1.2 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in dry EtOH (40 cm³), and 4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (1.6 g, 0.01 mol) was added to it. The mixture was heated under reflux (4 h) on water-bath. The yellow solution was filtered, volume reduced under vacuum and cooled to get yellow microcrystalline compound. It was recrystallised from EtOH, (75%), m.p. 178-180°. It is soluble in common organic solvents.

(H_2) DAMBHON : A solution of diacetyl (0.86 g, 0.01 mol) in EtOH (30 cm³) was added to a solution of 4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (3.3 g, 0.02 mol) in hot EtOH (40 cm³). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h and the white powder which separated out was filtered off and washed with EtOH and dried in vacuum (80%), m.p. 250°. The compound is soluble in coordinating solvents (e.g. DMSO) but insoluble in common organic solvents.

Preparation of complexes :

$Sn(DAMBHON)Cl_2$ (1) : To a hot EtOH (60 cm³) suspension of (H_2) DAMBHON (0.76 g, 0.002 mol) anhydrous $SnCl_4$ (0.52 g, 0.002 mol) was added under nitrogen atmosphere, and allowed to reflux for 30 min and filtered. Orange-yellow powder was obtained from the filtrate on cooling. It was filtered, washed several times with cold EtOH and then dried *in vacuo* (~70%), m.p. 250-55° d. The complex is soluble in DMF, DMSO, pyridine, nitromethane, chloroform, and methanol.

The same compound can also be isolated by the reaction of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the ligand in boiling ethanol in access of air.

$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})$ (2): This orange compound was obtained in solution when anhydrous SnCl_2 (0.38 g, 0.002 mol) and $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ (0.76 g, 0.002 mol) were reacted in boiling EtOH (50 cm^3) for 1 h. The orange coloured solid, which could be isolated from this solution on concentration and cooling, is extremely unstable towards aerial oxidation (see Discussion).

$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{Pr}^n)_2$ (3): Di-n-propyltin dichloride (1.4 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous acetone (50 cm^3) was added in nitrogen atmosphere to a boiling suspension of $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ (1.9 g, 0.005 mol) in dry MeOH (50 cm^3) and allowed to reflux for several min and filtered. The filtrate, on standing several days in a vacuum desiccator, yielded a bright yellow solid. It was filtered, washed with MeOH and dried *in vacuo* (70%), m.p. 225-27° d. The compound is soluble in MeOH , OCMe_2 , DMSO , DMF and pyridine.

$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})\text{R}_2$ (4, R=Ph; 5, R=Bu): These were similarly prepared by the reaction of $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ with Ph_2SnCl_2 and Bu_2SnCl_2 , respectively. The compounds are soluble in many organic solvents.

$\text{Sn}(\text{SMBHON})\text{R}_2$ (6, R=Ph; 7, R=Bu): $(\text{H}_2)\text{-SMBHON}$ (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) was taken in THF (100 cm^3), and NaH (0.53 g, about 10% excess over 0.002 mol) was added to it and heated to about 50° for 2 h. To the mixture was then added R_2SnCl_2 (0.002 mol) and stirred for 2 h at $50 \pm 2^\circ$ and filtered. The filtrate on concentration and cooling gave yellow (R=Ph) and brown yellow (R=Bu) solid in about 70% yield. Recrystallisation from THF -petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) mixture gave pure product: 6, m.p. > 300° and 7, 280-82° d. The compounds are soluble in coordinating solvents and also in many organic solvents.

$\text{Sn}\{(\text{H})\text{SMBHON}\}_2(\text{OH})_2$ (8): Solid $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.23 g, 0.001 mol) was added to a boiling solution of $(\text{H}_2)\text{SMBHON}$ (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) in EtOH (35 cm^3) (no care was taken to avoid the access of oxygen). The yellow solution formed was heated under reflux for 3 h. It was then filtered and volume of the filtrate was reduced to about 20 ml under vacuum and kept in a refrigerator for 3 days to get the product as a yellow powder (60%). The complex is soluble in DMF and DMSO and pyridine.

$\text{Pb}(\text{DAMBHON})$ (9): Sodium salt of the ligand was prepared by treating $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ with NaH in THF as described above, and subsequently reacted with PbCl_2 (1:1 molar ratio) in THF - EtOH mixture by refluxing for about 3 h. The resulting orange-yellow solution was filtered, concentrated and cooled to -20° to get a yellow-brown powder (50%), m.p. 250-52° d. The complex is soluble in MeOH , EtOH , pyridine, DMSO and DMF .

$\text{Pb}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{CH}_3)_2$ (10): The yellow compound was similarly prepared by refluxing (3 h) a mixture of NaH (0.02 mol), $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ (0.01 mol) and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{PbCl}_2$ (0.01 mol) in THF - MeOH mixture (500 cm^3), yield 70%, m.p. 268-70° d. The complex is soluble in MeOH , DMSO , DMF and pyridine.

$\text{Zr}\{(\text{H}_2)\text{SMBHON}\}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (11): $(\text{H}_2)\text{-SMBHON}$ (0.27 g, 0.001 mol) was dissolved in hot dry EtOH (25 cm^3). To the resulting light yellow solution, $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.32 g, 0.001 mol) was added and the mixture allowed to reflux on water-bath for 2 h and filtered. The yellow filtrate was concentrated under low pressure and kept in a refrigerator for 3 days. The yellow crystals were filtered off, and recrystallised from EtOH -petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) mixture to yield the product (80%), m.p. 243-45° d. The complex is soluble in MeOH , EtOH , $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$, DMF , DMSO and pyridine.

$\text{Zr}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{OH})_2(\text{THF})$ (12): The compound was prepared as yellow-brown powder by the reaction of $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ and $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.005 mol each) in THF in presence of NaH as described for the preparation of 5. The complex is soluble in coordinating solvents.

$\text{Zr}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ (13): The brown compound was similarly prepared from $(\text{H})\text{DAMBHON}$ and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ (0.005 mol each) in THF and in presence of NaH as described above, yield 75%, m.p. 280-82° d. The complex is soluble in coordinating solvents and also in many other organic solvents.

Some reactions of $\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})\text{Cl}_2$ (1):

With MeSH : 1 was added to MeSH (1:2 molar proportions) in nitromethane-toluene (50:50, v/v) and the mixture stirred at room temperature in the presence of a stoichiometric amount of NEt_3 for 2 days. After removal of Et_3N , HCl , the volume of the solution was reduced under vacuum, to yield yellow brown powder of $\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{SMe})_2$ (14) on cooling to $-20 \pm 5^\circ$. The compound was filtered off, washed with cold nitromethane and then with hexane and dried *in vacuo* (80%), m.p. 272-5° d.

With $\text{SiMe}_3(\text{NMe}_2)$: 1 was treated with an equimolar quantity of $\text{SiMe}_3(\text{NMe}_2)$ as above and $\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{NMe}_2)_2$ (15) was isolated (~65%), m.p. 208-10° d.

Physical measurements: Investigations of physical properties were carried out as described previously¹³⁻¹⁶.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis: The reactions of $(\text{H}_2)\text{SMBHON}$ and $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ with SnCl_4 , SnCl_2 , $\text{Pr}_2^2\text{SnCl}_2$, $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ under different reaction conditions yielded the coloured complexes 1-13. 1 reacted smoothly with MeSH and $\text{SiMe}_3(\text{NMe}_2)$ to yield thiolato- and amido-complexes of

tin(IV), respectively, $\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{L})_2$ (**14**, $\text{L}=\text{SMe}$; **15**, $\text{L}=\text{NMe}_2$). In connection with the synthesis of **15**, mention may be made that desilylation reactions have recently been demonstrated by us as the elegant route for the synthesis of new/novel coordination and organometallic compounds^{14,15,17}. Successful isolation of **15** by this desilylation route tempted us to investigate further in this direction and we allowed **1** to react with $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3$ and $p\text{-Me}_3\text{SiCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3$ at $5\pm 10^\circ$ leading thereby to the isolation of **16** and **17**, respectively in a very high yield (equations 1 and 2).

The new 6-coordinate organotin(IV) compounds **16** and **17** are formed with the elimination of Me_3SiCl . However, we failed to substitute both the Sn-Cl bonds in **1** even with excess of organo-

silicon substrates, the reason(s) of which is not clearly known to us at the moment. In any case, the novelty of desilylation is demonstrated by these reactions. (Details of these reactions are now being investigated). The elemental analysis and molecular weight (Table 1) support their formulations. The present results support that the aroylhydrazone, $(\text{H}_2)\text{DAMBHON}$ acts as a dibasic tetradentate ligand in the complexes **1-5**, **9**, **10**, **12-15**. On the other hand, $(\text{H}_2)\text{SMBHON}$ functions as a dibasic tridentate ligand in the complexes **6** and **7**, as a monobasic bidentate ligand in complex **8**, and as a neutral bidentate ligand in complex **11** (phenolic OH remaining free). The ability of the solvent to deprotonate such ligand is due to the increased acidity of the ligand proton caused by its coordination with the metal ions¹². It is known that coordination to transition metals may increase the acid dissociation constant of some hydrazone systems by a factor of 10^5 - 10^8 . It was also observed in the present study that repetition of the preparation of **8** in MeOH containing stoichiometric amounts of Na and in excess of air yielded a tin(IV) complex, $(\text{SMBHON})_2\text{Sn}$ (**8a**) (no OH group as indicated from ir spectroscopic data; correct C, H and N analyses). It is thus obvious that the said ligand $(\text{H}_2)\text{SMBHON}$ functions in a dibasic

 TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, MOLECULAR WEIGHT^a AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE^b VALUES OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Molecular weight:: Found/(Calcd.)	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
		C	H	N	Halide	Metal		
	$\text{H}_2(\text{SMBHON})$	—	—	10.07 (10.3)	—	—	—	—
	$\text{H}_2(\text{DAMBHON})$	—	—	14.03 (14.66)	—	—	—	—
1	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})\text{Cl}_2$	41.99 (42.13)	3.35 (3.51)	9.88 (9.85)	12.29 (12.46)	20.52 (20.83)	552 (569.79)	8.5
2	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})$	48.07 (48.12)	3.89 (4.01)	11.49 (11.29)	—	—	—	12.0
3	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{Pr}^n)_2$	53.80 (53.37)	6.00 (5.82)	9.48 (9.36)	—	20.58 (20.31)	598 (582.69)	9.1
4	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{Ph})_2$	59.02 (58.83)	4.88 (4.59)	8.76 (8.58)	—	18.20 (18.18)	614 (652.69)	10.8
5	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{Bu})_2$	54.72 (54.84)	5.28 (5.55)	9.22 (9.14)	—	19.58 (19.37)	—	8.9
6	$\text{Sn}(\text{SMBHON})(\text{Ph})_2$	60.08 (59.91)	4.41 (4.06)	5.00 (5.18)	—	21.28 (21.9)	580 (540.69)	11.0
7	$\text{Sn}(\text{SMBHON})(\text{Bu})_2$	55.68 (55.12)	6.23 (5.99)	5.88 (5.59)	—	24.09 (23.71)	—	11.6
8	$\text{Sn}\{(\text{H})\text{SMBHON}\}_2(\text{OH})_2$	52.88 (52.13)	4.04 (4.06)	8.29 (8.11)	—	17.59 (17.19)	—	10.9
9	$\text{Pb}(\text{DAMBHON})$	41.03 (40.88)	3.45 (3.41)	9.31 (9.54)	—	35.66 (35.30)	539 (587.2)	12.0
10	$\text{Pb}(\text{DAMBHON})\text{Me}_2$	43.14 (43.12)	4.00 (4.24)	9.44 (9.14)	—	38.11 (33.03)	590 (617.2)	9.8
11	$\text{Zr}\{(\text{H}_2)\text{SMBHON}\}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	37.65 (37.17)	3.49 (3.71)	5.30 (5.78)	—	18.35 (18.83)	439 (483)	12.0
12	$\text{Zr}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{OH})_2(\text{THF})$	50.04 (49.89)	5.11 (5.19)	9.88 (9.70)	—	15.98 (15.80)	—	10.2
13	$\text{Zr}(\text{DAMBHON})(\pi\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$	60.02 (59.88)	5.03 (4.99)	9.88 (9.32)	—	15.66 (15.17)	569 (600)	9.8
14	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{SMe})_2$	44.02 (44.54)	4.27 (4.38)	9.66 (9.45)	—	20.11 (20.02)	568 (591)	11.9
15	$\text{Sn}(\text{DAMBHON})(\text{NMe}_2)_2$	49.27 (49.08)	5.77 (5.45)	14.80 (14.32)	—	19.98 (20.23)	610 (583)	10.5

^a Osmometry. ^b 10^{-3} M solution in DMF.

tridentate manner in **8a**, while it acts as monobasic bidentate ligand in **8**.

Molar conductances: All the compounds isolated in the present study behave as non-electrolytes in DMF (Λ_M of 10^{-3} M solution at room temperature varies between $8-12 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)¹⁸ (Table 1).

Uv-vis spectra: The free ligands show absorption bands in the regions 230-245, 280-295 and 330-340 nm. The complexes, on the other hand, show bands in the region 220-230, 250-270 nm and a very broad band in the region 340-450 nm. The observed shifts of the ligand bands along with the appearance of a new broad band in the region 340-450 nm (may be considered as charge transfer transition) in the spectra of the complexes may be taken as an evidence of coordination of the ligands to the metals.

The tin(II) compound Sn(DAMBHON) (**2**) is stable only in nitrogen atmosphere. This tin(II) species slowly oxidised to tin(IV), as is evidenced from the electronic spectra (400-700 nm region) of Sn(DAMBHON) in DMSO under nitrogen atmosphere and in air (Fig. 1). Similar observations were made earlier with tin(II)-porphyrin and -phthalocyanine complexes¹⁹. The electronic spectra of the complex Sn(DAMBHON)Cl₂ (**1**) is similar to that of the complex **2**, recorded after aerial oxidation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Uv-vis spectra of Sn^{II} and Sn^{IV} compounds (visible and the near uv spectra are from different run): (—) Sn^{IV} (DAMBHON)Cl₂ (**1**) (in DMSO in air), (.....) Sn^{II} (DAMBHON) (**2**) (in DMSO after stirring 8 h in air) and (—) Sn^{II} (DAMBHON) (**2**) (in DMSO under N₂).

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr disc. The free ligands show bands for ν_{NH} around $3280-3310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which disappeared in the complexes **1-10** and **12-15** suggesting that the ligands act in the enol-form and bind with the metal ions after deprotonation. This ν_{NH} band in the complex **11** remains almost unaffected, which lends support to the keto-form of the ligand (H₂)SMBHON. Besides, the presence of medium to weak and broad bands in the region

$3300-3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes **8** and **11** suggest non-involvement of phenolic OH group in bond formation, while in the other complexes involvement of phenolic OH (after deprotonation) in bond formation is indicated by the disappearance of these bands. However, presence of OH group bonded to tin(IV) in **8** and zirconium(IV) in **11** complicates this situation.

The uncomplexed ligands exhibit amide I, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, amide II and amide III bands at about $1630-1665$, $1610-1620$, $1565-1575$, $1490-1495$ and 1265 cm^{-1} , respectively. Negative shifts of amide I ($\Delta\nu=10-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ ($\Delta\nu=20-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and amide II ($\Delta\nu=10-20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a positive shift ($\Delta\nu=15-25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of amide III in the spectra of the complex **11** indicate neutral nature of the ligand (H₂)SMBHON and coordination through carbonyl oxygen. These bands disappear in the deprotonated complexes **1-10** and **12-15** of both the ligands (H₂)SMBHON and (H₂)DAMBHON suggesting enolisation of the keto group followed by the formation of complexes through deprotonation. However, the presence of very strong and sharp band(s) around $1595-1615$ is diagnostic of the azine chromophore (C=N-N=C)²⁰. The vibrations observed around $1510-1550$ and $1330-1380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are characteristic of ν_{NCO} ²¹. In the free ligand, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ appears around $1610-1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, while this band shifted to around $1595-1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting coordination of azomethine nitrogen^{22,23}.

The band observed around $3250-3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complex **11** may be assigned to ν_{OH} of phenolic OH and of H₂O. The presence of a band at $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in this complex indicates the presence of coordinated H₂O, which is further supported by the appearance of wagging modes of H₂O at about 940 and 755 cm^{-1} , respectively²⁴.

¹H nmr spectra: The ¹H nmr spectral data together with assignments of some representative compounds are given in Table 2.

The free ligands (H₂)SMBHON and (H₂)DAMBHON show signals at $\delta 11.3$ and 11.5 , respectively which may be assigned to NH proton. This is absent in the complexes **1-10** and **12-15** indicating thereby the enolisation followed by deprotonation of the ligands while complexing with metal ions. On the other hand, this NH proton resonance in the complexes **11** observed at around $\delta 5.8$ as a broad singlet. This indicates that NH proton undergoes considerable shift in these complexes and thus supports coordination of ketonic oxygen. The phenolic proton resonances, on the other hand, remain unaffected in the complexes **8** and **11**, while these resonances in the other complexes (Table 2) disappeared upon complexation of the ligands. In addition, the sharp signals for C₆H₅, CH₃S and (CH₃)₂N in the complexes **13-15**, respectively, suggest a *trans* arrangement of these ligands, as shown below. On the basis of the above discussion the following structures may tentatively be proposed for the complexes isolated in the present study.

TABLE 2—¹H nmr SPECTRAL DATA (δ)^a OF SOME COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Compd. ^b	NH	OH(Ph)	OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ /SMe/NMe ₂
1	Sn(DAMBHON)Cl ₂ ^c	—	—	3.8	—
6	Sn(SAMBHON)Ph ₂ ^c	—	—	3.7	—
9	Pb(DAMBHON) ^c	—	—	3.8	—
13	Zr(DAMBHON)(π-O ₆ H ₆) ₂ ^c	—	—	3.75	6.8 (s)
14	Sn(DAMBHON)(SMe) ₂ ^c	—	—	3.75	3.40 (s)
15	Sn(DAMBHON)(NMe ₂) ₂ ^c	—	—	3.75	3.50 (s)
	(H ₂)SMBHON ^d	11.8	12.3	3.75	—
	(H ₂)DAMBHON ^c	11.5	12.6	3.78	—

^a TMS internal reference; right integrations obtained. ^b N=OH resonances in the complexes at δ 8.1–8.2 (around 8.5 ppm in free ligand); Ph-H absorbs at δ 6.3–6.6 (at 6.5–6.9 ppm in free ligand); singlet due to OH₂ of CH₃C=N— group experience a deshielding of about δ 0.5 due to coordination of imine nitrogen with the metal ions. ^c In CD₃NO₂. ^d In CD₃OD.

However, we are not sure about the structures of the complexes M(DAMBHON) 2, M=Sn^{II}; 9, M=Pd^{II}, although the possibility of attaining a ψ-trigonal bipyramidal structure cannot be ruled out²⁴.

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|------|-------------------------------------|------|-----|------|
| (1) | R=Cl; | M=Sn | (6) | R=Ph |
| (3) | R=Pr ⁿ ; | M=Sn | (7) | R=Bu |
| (4) | R=Ph; | M=Sn | | |
| (5) | R=Bu; | M=Sn | | |
| (10) | R=Me; | M=Pb | | |
| (12) | R=OH; | M=Zr | | |
| (13) | R=π-O ₆ H ₆ ; | M=Zr | | |
| (14) | R=SMe; | M=Sn | | |
| (15) | R=NMe ₂ ; | M=Sn | | |

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